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INTEGRATING THIRD-PARTY FLEXIBILITY RESOURCES INTO DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS: A QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT ON THE INTERACTIONS OF NETWORK TARIFFS AND LOCAL MARKETS

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Abstract

This paper explores innovative approaches to enhance the use of flexibility for electrical distribution networks by integrating time-of-use tariffs and local markets for DSO services. The study presents an analysis through a case study of three distinct scenarios. The first scenario examines the impact of the simultaneous operation of heat pump and electric vehicle loads, leading to significant congestion issues within the network. It highlights the challenges posed by the increasing presence of flexible loads without any pricing signals to guide their operation. In the second scenario, price signals based on time block and contracted capacity charges are introduced, demonstrating how these signals can effectively alleviate network congestion but could shift problems to other hours. The third scenario combines the benefits of tariffs with a local market, resulting in the most significant reduction in grid congestion. Consequently, the outcomes of the current analysis could support regulators and policymakers in designing efficient acquisition mechanisms tailored to the characteristics of the context to which they apply.

1 Introduction

The ongoing transformation of electrical distribution networks, driven by the dynamic landscape of the energy transition, is characterized by the increasing of intermittent renewable sources (i.e., solar, wind), electrification of critical sectors (i.e., transportation, industrial, heating), and the spread of distributed energy resources. This scenario requires the adoption of innovative approaches for acquiring distribution system operator (DSO) services [1]. These DSO services, like congestion management or voltage control, can be employed to exploit the potential flexibility from grid-connected third-party resources, including distributed generation units, active customers, and energy storage facilities, through acquisition mechanisms, such as network tariffs and local markets [2].

Network tariffs and local markets, traditionally designed for operating as independent entities, are reevaluated in the current paper under a combined assessment. By leveraging synergies between these mechanisms, the operation of distribution systems can be optimized for delaying or indefinitely deferring unnecessary network reinforcement, considering economical and technical perspectives [3], [4]. The potential for the joint design of these acquisition mechanisms lies in the ability of network tariffs and local markets to impact network usage patterns on both the supply and demand sides. This paper considers tariffs to reflect real-time system conditions and costs as an implicit flexibility mechanism for encouraging customers to adjust their energy behaviours in response to economic signals. Parallel, local markets incentivize participants to provide explicit flexibility services, offering

tangible incentives to support investments in energy resources and demand-side management strategies.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the models developed for this analysis. The first one models heat pump (HP) and electric vehicle (EV) loads to function as flexible demand by optimizing their power consumption to minimize operational costs. The second one models a local market for DSO services, primarily focusing on congestion management with active power. The first model examines how flexible resources react to price signals and affect the electrical grid, while the second model explores how a local market can enhance these price signals in the electricity costs to solve network congestion. Section 3 describes the case study and presents the input data employed. Section 4 examines the case study results across three scenarios: the first scenario uses an electricity cost profile without price signals based on a daily energy market. The second scenario employs a tariff that incorporates price signals in the form of time block and contracted capacity charges. The third scenario assesses the impact of combining scenario 2 with a local market to address network congestion. Finally, conclusions are presented in section 5.

2. Model description

Heat pumps and electric vehicles require to be modelled as flexible loads to respond to electricity prices and for local market participation. Table 1 details the indices, sets, parameters, and variables used in the formulation of both models.

Table 1 Indices, sets, parameters, and variables

Index, set	Description	Unit
$h \in H$	Index and set for time steps	hour
$hp \in nHP$	Index and set for HP types	number
$ev \in nEV$	Index and set for EV types	number
Parameter	Description	Unit
EC_h	Electricity cost	€/kWh
P_{cont}^{max}	Contracted capacity	kW
<i>Heat Pump model</i>		
COP_{hp}	Coefficients of performance	-
PHP_{hp}^{max}	Heat pump rated power	kW
T_{hp}^{out}	Outdoor temperature	°C
$T_{hp}^{min}, T_{hp}^{max}$	Min and max indoor temperatures	°C
$Q_{hp,h}^{loss}, Q_{hp,h}^{rad}$	Heat losses, and Solar radiation	kWh
<i>Electric Vehicle model</i>		
PEV_{ev}^{max}	Charger rated power	kW
η_{ev}	Charging efficiency	%
E_{ev}^{max}, DD_{ev}	Battery size, and daily demand	kWh
$h_{ev}^{arr}, h_{ev}^{dep}$	Arrival and Departure times	hour
SoC_{ev}^{dep}	Min charge at departure time	%
SoC_{ev}^{min}	Min SoC	%
<i>Local market model</i>		
$C_{f,h}^{UP}, C_{f,h}^{DP}$	Upwards and downwards flexibility cost	€/kW
C^β	Cost of flexibility not supplied	€/kVA
$\Delta S_{cl,h}$	Congestion management flexibility needs	kVA
$K_{cl,f}^P$	Sensitivity factor	kVA/kW
$P_{f,h}^{Umax}, P_{f,h}^{Dmax}$	Upwards and downwards flexibility bid limits	kW
Variable	Description	Unit
<i>Heat Pump model</i>		
$pHP_{hp,h}$	Power consumptions of HPs	kW
$t_{hp,h}$	Indoor temperature	°C
$q_{hp,h}, q_{hp,h}^i$	Indoor heat, and HP heat	kWh
$t_{hp,h}^w, t_{hp,h}^r$	Wall and roof temperatures	°C
<i>Electric Vehicle model</i>		
$pEV_{ev,h}$	Power consumptions of EVs	kW
$soC_{ev,h}$	State of Charge of EV batteries	%
<i>Local market model</i>		
$\Delta p_{f,h}^U, \Delta p_{f,h}^D$	Upward and downward flexibility cleared bids (active power)	kW
$\beta_{cl,h}$	Not supplied flexibility	kVA
$p_{f,h}, q_{f,h}, s_{f,h}$	Flexibility providers power variables	kW, kVAR, kVA

Model for the electricity cost responses of HPs and EVs

The objective function in (1) aims to minimize the operational costs for the HP and EV loads across all simulation time steps.

$$\min \sum_{ev, hp, h} (pHP_{hp,h} + pEV_{ev,h}) \times EC_h \quad (1)$$

Equations (2) to (6) describe the constrains for the heat pump model. Equations (2) and (3) limit the consumption of the

HPs considering conversion efficiency, environmental characteristics, and the operating temperature range.

$$pHP_{hp,h} \times COP_{hp} = q_{hp,h}^i \quad (2)$$

$$pHP_{hp,h} \leq PHP_{hp}^{max} \quad (3)$$

$$q_{hp,h}^i = q_{hp,h} + Q_{hp,h}^{loss} - Q_{hp,h}^{rad} \quad (4)$$

$$T_{hp}^{min} \leq t_{hp,h} \leq T_{hp}^{max} \quad (5)$$

The group of constraints in (6) describe the house thermal balance according to the model proposed in [5].

$$(T_{hp}^{out}, t_{w,h}, t_{r,h}) \in \Psi \quad (6)$$

Equations (7) to (12) present the constraints for the electric vehicle model. This model is developed exclusively for a load configuration that focuses solely on the charging process. Here (7) and (8), limit the required power to the charger capacity when EVs are connected to the grid.

$$0 \leq pEV_{ev,h} \leq \phi_{ev,h} \times PEV_{ev}^{max} \quad (7)$$

$$\phi_{ev,h} = \begin{cases} 1, & h_{ev}^{arr} \leq h \leq h_{ev}^{dep} \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Equations (9) to (12) constrains the State of Charge (SoC) of EV batteries. These constrains consider the maximum battery capacity and daily demand. It also sets a minimum charge level required before the disconnection of the EVs, as the minimum to preserve the lifetime of the battery.

$$soC_{ev,h} = soC_{ev,h-1} + pEV_{ev,h-1} \times (\eta_{ev}/E_{ev}^{max}) \quad (9)$$

$$soC_{ev,h=h_{ev}^{arr}} = 1 - DD_{ev}/E_{ev}^{max} \quad (10)$$

$$soC_{ev,h=h_{ev}^{dep}} \geq SoC_{ev}^{dep} \quad (11)$$

$$SoC_{ev}^{min} \leq soC_{ev,h} \leq 100\% \quad (12)$$

Additionally, the constraint (13) addresses the contracted capacity limit according to the tariff design.

$$pHP_{hp,h} + pEV_{ev,h} \leq P_{cont}^{max} \quad (13)$$

Local Market model

As formulated in (14), the local market model for congestion management aims to minimize both the flexibility procurement cost in terms of active power and the cost associated with the not supplied flexibility $\beta_{cl,h}$.

$$\min \sum_h \left(\sum_f [C_{f,h}^{UP} \times \Delta p_{f,h}^U + C_{f,h}^{DP} \times \Delta p_{f,h}^D] + \sum_{cl} C^\beta \times |\beta_{cl,h}| \right) \quad (14)$$

This objective function is subject to constraints (15) - (18), where (15) matches the DSO flexibility needs $\Delta S_{cl,h}$ with the upward and downward bids from flexibility providers. When the available flexibility is insufficient to meet these needs, $\beta_{cl,h}$ takes a non-zero value. Additionally, constraints (16) and (17) capture the limits of the submitted flexibility bids, while

the set of constraints in (18) represents the required equations for modelling the capability limits of flexibility providers.

$$\Delta S_{cl,h} \leq \sum_f [K_{cl,f}^P \times (\Delta p_{f,h}^U - \Delta p_{f,h}^D)] + \beta_{cl,h} \quad (15)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{f,h}^U \leq P_{f,h}^{Umax} \quad (16)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{f,h}^D \leq P_{f,h}^{Dmax} \quad (17)$$

$$(\Delta p_{f,h}^U, \Delta p_{f,h}^D, p_{f,h}, q_{f,h}, s_{f,h}) \in \Phi \quad (18)$$

3. Case study

The case study aims to evaluate the impact of tariff designs and the local market for DSO services on mitigating transformer and line overloading. It explores three scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Assessing the impact of volumetric tariffs based only on daily market (SPOT) prices. Electricity costs in Spain are used for this scenario.
- Scenario 2: Evaluating the impact of tariff designs with time block and capacity limitation charges (€/kW). The current methodology in Spain for the voluntary price for the small consumer (PVPC) is used as a reference.
- Scenario 3: Combining the PVPC scenario and the local market for DSO services model.

A simplified network model, incorporating several types of grid resources, is employed in all scenarios. The analyses focus on a single representative day (24 hours) to assess the flexibility solutions under typical conditions.

Network model description.

The simplified network model depicted in Fig. 1 is based on the Dickert LV Network [6], and has been adapted according to the case study requirements. This grid comprises a medium-to-low voltage radial topology with one single transformation centre and two main feeders (F0 with no branching and F1 with simple branching into F1A and F1B). The network includes 14 buses as delivery points, 10 aggregated loads with residential demand profiles (R), 8 loads with industrial demand profiles (I), and 9 photovoltaic (PV) systems for distributed generation. These resources are not used to acquire DSO services. Flexible resources are incorporated through HP and EV loads.

Input Data

Fig. 2 shows the main input data. The Fig. 2a) illustrates the generic profiles [7] assigned in the network model for non-flexible resources, including residential and industrial loads, as well as PV generation profiles. These normalized data ensure comparability with flexible loads (HPs and EVs). Fig. 2b) depicts the temperature profile employed in the heat pump model. For this analysis, a representative day of low temperature has been selected (January 23, 2023). This data is used to assess the performance of the heat pump model, as its operation depends on temperature variations. Fig. 2c) showcases the electricity prices for the same representative

Fig. 1 Network model (HP and EV are the flexible loads)

day. The resultant electricity costs from the SPOT market and the PVPC in Spain are employed. It can be noted how the PVPC tariff fluctuates regarding SPOT prices across different block periods, reflecting the impact of the time block charges, further information in [8].

Fig. 2 Input data (a) Generic profiles for generation and demand, (b) Outdoor temperature, (c) Electricity costs.

Flexible demand configuration.

HPs and EVs are designated as flexible loads to assess the impact when responding to price signals in tariff designs (Scenario 2) and interacting with a local market (Scenario 3). A specific number of HPs and EVs are allocated as illustrated in Fig. 1. Several parameters and design criteria have been

established for both HP and EV loads. Table 2 shows the parameters for the heat pump load model. Five types of heat pumps (HP1 to HP5) are shaping varying the COP, with a mean of 4 and a standard deviation of 0.4. Also, five room environments (indoor characteristics) are configured for the house thermal balance model, where the most efficient heat pump is assigned to the room with the best insulation parameters, while the least efficient heat pump is assigned to the room with the worst insulation parameters. This configuration represents an HP instance. As expected, the power consumption from the most efficient HP instance (HP5) is lower than the least efficient (HP1). The rated power is set at 3.0 kW considering residential or office applications. For allowing comparison under the same external conditions, a comfortable range between 20°C and 25°C has been assumed for all HP instances. Consequently, fifteen heat pump are assigned to each bus with HP loads, comprising three sets of five different HP instances.

Table 2 HP loads parameter

Parameter	Value
COP mean and std	4 ± 0.4
Rated power	3.0 kW
Range indoor temperature	20 °C to 25 °C

Table 3 shows the parameters employed in the EV load model. The different EV instances (EV1 to EV3) are characterized by the charger rated power, battery autonomy, daily demand for the battery, arrival time, and departure time shown in Table 3. For comparability, it has been considered a normal charging with 7.5 kW for the charger rated power, charging efficiency of 90%, and SoC of 80% before departure, with a minimum of 20% to preserve the battery life. For each EV bus in the network model, nine EV loads are assigned, consisting of three groups of the three different EV instances.

Table 3 EV loads parameter

Parameter	Value
Charger rated power	7.5 kW
Charging efficiency	90%
Battery size	60 ± 20 kWh
Daily Demand	12 ± 2 kWh
Arrival Time	9 ± 1 hour
Departure Time	18 ± 1 hour
Minimum SoC at departure time	80%
Minimum SoC	20%

Local markets parameters

Table 4 outlines the parameters for the local market configuration. The flexible demand participating in the market clearing are the HP and EV loads. Since the market model is exclusively for congestion management with active power, a sensitivity analysis has been carried out for different percentages for upward and downward active power bids. The offer prices, only for activation, are set randomly with a mean of 35€ and a standard deviation of 0.244€. These prices are based on PICLO initiative [9].

Table 4 Local market parameter

Parameter	Value
Percentage of flexibility (upwards/downwards) for active power	5%, 10%, 15%, 19.17%
Upward/downward bids mean and std	35 € ± 0.244 €
Beta costs	7880 €

4 Results

This section presents the findings from the three scenarios of the case study, providing insights into how each approach impacts congestion problems in the network.

Scenario 1: HPs and EVs with SPOT prices.

Fig. 3 presents the results for Scenario 1, where only the SPOT prices profile from Fig. 2c) (green-coloured graph) is employed. These do not necessarily match the actual electricity costs. However, in a network tariff design based on these prices, the electricity costs follow a proportional trend. Therefore, this price profile serves as a reference.

Fig. 3 Scenario 1: Individual profiles of HP and EV loads considering SPOT prices. a) Power consumption profiles, b) Indoor temperature for HPs, c) State of Charge for EVs.

Fig. 3a) shows the individual power profiles of the heat pump (HP1 to HP5) and electric vehicle (EV1 to EV3) loads. The model in section 2 optimizes the power consumption, minimizing the associated costs of the HP and EV loads operation. The HPs can be activated at any time, but depend on environmental conditions (Fig. 2b)) to keep the indoor temperature within the set limits. The EVs depend on their dwell time to the electrical grid established between the arrival and departure times.

Fig. 3a) shows that the HP loads operate several times throughout the day to maintain indoor temperature conditions (Fig. 3b)), with significant power consumption at 5:00 (lowest outdoor temperature) and at 15:00 (decreasing outdoor and

indoor temperatures). The EV loads operate between 14:00 to 16:00 to meet battery charging requirements (Fig. 3c)), with a peak consumption at 15:00. The HP and EV loads respond not only to the aforementioned factors but also to the lowest electricity prices.

Fig. 4 shows the percentage loading for the transformer and all network lines, considering both flexible loads and non-flexible resources. The main hours for examination are 5:00, 11:00 and 15:00, where several components are either congested or close to their allowable thermal limits. The hours of 5:00 and 15:00 are not critical for non-flexible loads but are critical for HP and EV loads. This could mean that the aggregated consumptions of these flexible loads are causing congestion issues in certain components due to excessive demand. At 11:00, the maximum PV production occurs, so these congestions could be caused by excessive generation.

Fig. 4 Scenario 1: Loading percentage of the trafo and lines

Table 5 summarizes the flexibility requirements for the congested transformer and lines for the scenario 1. In this scenario, the flexibility needs are concentrated mainly at two specific hours, with a total demand of 0.2182 MW.

Table 5 Flexibility needs for Scenario 1

Name	Hour	Loading, %	Flexibility needs, MW
Trafo T0	15	114.11	0.0536
Line F0-L0	15	132.40	0.0548
Line F0-L1	15	130.84	0.0548
Line F1-L0	15	111.03	0.0196
Line F1-L1	15	112.19	0.0217
Line F1B-L0	11	106.13	0.0108
Total flexibility required, MW			0.2182

Scenario 2: HPs and EVs with PVPC prices.

Scenario 2 considers electricity cost based on the PVPC tariff (Fig. 2c) (red-coloured graph) with time block and capacity charges. For those users with both HP and EV, a contracted capacity of 10kW is assumed. The results are shown in Fig. 5. The power consumptions in Fig. 5a) of HP and EV loads have changed compared to Fig. 3a). For HP loads, power consumption at 5:00 has increased while still maintaining the indoor temperature within the allowed ranges Fig. 5b). A second peak in power consumption, although slightly smaller, has shifted to 17:00, coinciding with a period of lower non-flexible load consumption (Fig. 2a). For EV loads, they continue operating between 14:00 and 16:00 to meet battery SoC requirements (Fig. 5c)), with a peak at 14:00. HP and EV

loads continue responding to operational cost minimization, but now according to the PVPC tariff.

Fig. 5 Scenario 2: Individual profiles of HP and EV models considering PVPC prices

Fig. 6 illustrates how transformer and lines congestion are impacted in response to the shifted consumption patterns driven by a different tariff design. It is observed that the critical hours are now at 5:00 and 11:00. The previous congestion issues at 15:00 have been reduced.

Fig. 6 Scenario 2: Loading percentage of the trafo and lines

Table 6 details the flexibility requirements for the congested transformer and lines in Scenario 2. Although the number of congestion events has increased compared to Scenario 1, the overall flexibility needs have decreased to 0.1995 MW, as well as those affected specifically by flexible loads. The HP loads, which previously operated with lower consumption at 5:00, now need to run at that time, leading to this effect.

Table 6 Flexibility needs for Scenario 2

Name	Hour	Loading, %	Flexibility needs, MW
Trafo T0	5	113.81	0.0524
Line F0-L0	5	132.16	0.0571
Line F0-L1	5	123.98	0.0426
Line F1-L0	5	110.60	0.0188
Line F1-L1	5	106.01	0.0107
Line F1B-L0	11	107.42	0.0132
Line F1-L0	11	102.53	0.0045
Total flexibility required, MW			0.1995

Scenario 3: Analysis of HPs and EVs impact with PVPC prices and Local Market for DSO services.

Scenario 3 analyses the interaction between network tariffs from scenario 2 and the local market model for congestion management. These mechanisms have been widely studied as independent entities, but their interactions remain unclear. Thus, the outcomes of this scenario may provide insights into their joint potential to avoid network issues. Since the same tariffs from Scenario 2 are employed, the flexible load consumption patterns remain unchanged, and these profiles are employed for the local market clearing with the parameters in Table 4. Additionally, a post-evaluation was conducted to assess the impact on the network. Fig. 7 shows the results.

Fig. 7 Flexibility needs for each sensitivity in Scenario 3

Similar to Scenario 2, the critical hours remain at 5:00 and 11:00. However, compared to Scenario 2, congestion events are reduced, and the total flexibility required have notably decreased as the percentage of flexibility offered in the market by the HP and EV loads increase from 5% to 19.17%. At this latter percentage, the congestion created by the demand at 5:00 are completely resolved and the total flexibility required has been diminished to 0.0177 MW. The congestion caused by generation at 11:00 persist from scenario 2. However, this issue can be addressed by leveraging connected resources that provide downward flexibility or by employing other acquisition mechanism, like flexible connection agreements that allow for curtailment under specific conditions.

5 Conclusions

Incorporating network tariffs that reflect real-time system conditions with local markets that incentivize explicit flexibility shows great potential for enhancing network usage. In this paper, we analyse a case study with three scenarios to assess the combined effects of those mechanisms. In Scenario 1, the operation of HP and EV loads create network congestion. By including price signals based on time-blocks

and capacity charges in Scenario 2, we observe how network congestion is reduced. Scenario 3 demonstrates that price signals in electricity costs with a local market for DSO services reduce network constraints. Future developments should consider not only electricity costs but also more efficient tariff structures, e.g., incremental network tariffs designed to incorporate signals to reduce future network and generation costs. Also, consider local markets that include more products and services. Efficient network tariffs or a combination with local markets show a great potential to exploit the flexibility of the resources connected to the power system. The final solution would depend on the regulatory, techno-economic and social contexts for activating flexibility.

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